

INTERNAL TEMPERATURE AND THERMAL GRADIENT SENSING OF COMPOSITES VIA NANOROD PLASMON RESONANCE SPECTROSCOPY

Jeffery W. Baur¹, W. Joshua Kennedy^{1,2}, Keith A. Slinker^{1,2},
Brent Volk¹, Hilmar Koerner¹, and Gregory J. Ehlert¹

¹Materials and Manufacturing Directorate
Air Force Research Laboratory
AFRL/RXCC 2941 Hobson Way
Wright-Patterson AFB, OH 45433
USA
Email: Jeffery.Baur@us.af.mil

²Universal Technology Corporation
1270 North Fairfield Road
Dayton, Ohio 45432

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ABSTRACT

A new method is developed for the determination of internal temperatures and spatially resolved thermal gradients using the change in aspect ratio of dispersed gold nanorods and corresponding changes in their measured plasmon resonance spectrum. Previously, changes in the plasmon resonance spectral peaks of gold nanorods as a function of temperature were observed by several researchers in solution. These spectral shifts were related to the change in aspect ratio of the nanorods as they transitioned continuously from an elongated ellipsoid towards a sphere. Aspect ratios are confirmed with X-ray scattering and TEM microscopy. When the gold nanorods are dispersed in a structural epoxy resin, their spectral changes are used to infer the steady state temperature over a range of temperatures and thermal gradients. Using spatially resolved spectroscopy, an extension of current theory, and isothermal calibration curves, we demonstrate that the maximum temperature experienced within a composite can be spatially mapped over a useful temperature and temporal range. This provides an important means of understanding a composite's thermal history and to validate thermal models without disrupting the composite structures by either embedded thermocouples or inferring the internal temperature from surface thermal measurements. The technique requires very low loading of materials (<0.05vol%) and has a spatial limitation limited by the optical detection system being employed. We measure thermal gradients of $>1^{\circ}\text{C}/\mu\text{m}$ within an epoxy resin in the proximity of a single carbon fiber that is resistively heated. We compare the measurements with continuum models and obtain good agreement. We also demonstrate the applicability of the approach to macroscale thermal gradient measurements. A gradient of $4^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{mm}$ was measured with comparable capability to a commercial thermal camera. The general applicability of this approach to other thermally sensitive nanomaterials and for validation of composite processing models will be discussed.

1 INTRODUCTION

Control of thermal gradients is an important capability for the production, machining, and operational processes of composite materials. For example, thermoset cure processes rely on precise thermal cycles. However, maintaining isothermal profiles throughout a structure during processing is difficult to achieve in practice. Conversely, high energy processes such as laser machining of composites involve very large thermal gradients. The extent of the heat affected zone determines the quality of the cut and has limited the wide spread adoption of laser machining of polymer composites. In recent years, a large effort has been made to develop integrated computational materials engineering (ICME) for composite materials to better predict a component's properties, dimensions, performance, and life. In order to inform and validate computational tools, it is necessary to know what internal

temperatures a composite material experiences. In some cases, it is crucial that this information be determined at high spatial resolution.

Gold nanorods (AuNRs) are known to change their shape from cylindrical to ovoid or spheroid under the influence of both environmental heat and direct heating via laser irradiation[1]–[6]. This thermal shape transformation leads to a correlation between the temperature of a gold nanorod and its optical absorption, which is dependent on rod shape and size. AuNRs are reshaped to an extent depending on a number of factors, including the absolute size of the particle, crystal structure and defects, and the nature of the interface with the surrounding medium. When embedded in a polymer matrix, the final shape of AuNRs is directly correlated with the steady state temperature[7],[8]. In this work, we have developed a technique that enables the microscale, ex-situ measurement of temperature within a structural epoxy by exploiting this thermally induced shape change. We use a modified expression for the AuNR optical scattering, based on classical Mie-Gans theory, to correlate the final aspect ratio to temperature. We then use the calibration to determine the maximum temperature experienced within a sample by spatially mapping the optical absorption. We demonstrate the usefulness of this technique in a model system consisting of a single fiber surrounded by a structural epoxy. We measure the temperature gradient ($>1^\circ\text{C}/\mu\text{m}$) around the fiber with a spatial resolution of at least $10\ \mu\text{m}$. We compare our measurements with finite element analysis of the heat flow and find agreement within $\pm 5^\circ\text{C}$.

2 TEMPERATURE CALIBRATION

The optical scattering of AuNRs is dominated by surface plasmon resonances in the directions longitudinal and transverse to the nanorod axis. When the rods are small, this scattering is well described by classical Mie-Gans theory, which predicts that the optical scattering will depend on, among other things, the particle's aspect ratio[9]. Thus, in order to obtain thermal information from the nanorod spectra, it is important to understand how the AuNRs change their shape with temperature. Unfortunately, there is no universally accepted physical mechanism for the transformation. The phenomenon is primarily driven by the competition between surface energy minimization and recrystallization within a surface melt layer (or virtual melt)[7], [10]–[12]. In the simplest of cases, the diffusion of the surface atoms (or flow of the surface melt layer) leads to an Arrhenius behavior in the rate of change of the geometric aspect ratio of the rods. The exact mechanism of the shape transformation of AuNRs is not fully understood, and no analytical expression exists to describe the characteristic relaxation time as a function of all the physical variables. Unlike a pure Arrhenius-type reaction, the time evolution of the aspect ratio of AuNRs in epoxy decays biexponentially (see **Figure 2** and discussion below). Regardless of the specific mechanism, the thermal reshaping of AuNRs embedded in polymer matrices proceeds at a rate that is initially rapid but then diminishes over time as the aspect ratio asymptotically approaches a final value that depends on the temperature[8]. It is the slower changing regime which most readily lends itself to simplified detection and unique correlation with temperature. This behavior allows for the calibration of the temperature response provided the heating times are longer than the time of the rapid change in aspect ratios.

An illustration of the temperature detection mechanism is shown in **Figure 1**. A plot is shown of the theoretical spectral shifts in scattering spectra as a result of thermally induced changes to the aspect ratio (a) and the local dielectric constant (ϵ). The schematic shows how the AuNRs respond to a radial thermal gradient such as the one discussed in the next section. The samples were fabricated by suspending the AuNRs in isopropanol and mixing with epoxy resin (EPON 828 with Jeffamine D230 @ 100:35) to obtain a nanocomposite (AuNR-EPON). The epoxy was poured into a silicone mold and cured at 40°C for 6 hours. The temperature response of the nanorods in AuNR-EPON was calibrated by measuring their absorption spectra while being subjected to isothermal holds at a variety of temperatures. **Figure 2a** shows a few representative spectra for AuNR-EPON at 160°C along with the Gaussian fit curves used to determine the plasmon resonance energies. Mie-Gans theory was used to calculate the AuNR aspect ratio independently from the dielectric constant of the surrounding material. The transformation of the aspect ratio over time is shown in **Figure 2b** for several

temperatures between 100° and 200° C. The dependence on temperature of the final aspect ratio a_{∞} is shown in **Figure 1c**, and it forms the basis for the temperature calibration.

3 APPLICATION UNDER CONTROLLED THERMAL GRADIENTS

Once the thermal response of the AuNRs in a given material has been calibrated, it is a straightforward process to obtain a map of the steady state temperature experienced by a test specimen. The measurement is accomplished by following the following protocol:

- 1) Heat the sample in the desired configuration over a time sufficient for the AuNRs to approach their asymptotic limits. For AuNR-EPON, sample temperatures of over 100° C for three hour heating periods guarantee that the AuNRs have experienced >95% of the possible change. Shorter times are needed for higher temperatures.
- 2) Cut sections of the sample transverse to the desired profile geometry. Specimen thicknesses should be large enough to provide enough absorbance to clearly resolve both plasmon resonance peaks.
- 3) Obtain scattering/absorption spectra of the AuNRs in the matrix via a microspectrophotometer or other high resolution device. Raster over the specimen to produce a hyperspectral map.
- 4) For each pixel, calculate the aspect ratio from the spectrum and then apply the calibration to determine the temperature.

As a demonstration of the usefulness and accuracy of this temperature sensing method, samples were subjected to a variety of thermal gradients, and steady-state temperature maps were generated for each configuration. For example, **Figure 4** shows a temperature map obtained from a rectangular specimen that was heated at one end with a hot-stage and cooled at the other end with a copper cold finger. For comparison, a FLIR image of the same sample during heating is shown, and the average temperature profile along the length of the sample is plotted for both measurements.

A more complex heating geometry is shown in **Figure 5**. A single carbon fiber was embedded in a strip of AuNR-EPON in a dog-bone shape. The fiber was heated resistively via electrical contacts at each end of the dog-bone. This resulted in a complex, three-dimensional temperature field. The thermal profile can be visualized via radiography (**Figure 5b**) and finite element analysis (**Figure 5c**). Two cross-sections of this sample were cut at locations **A** and **B** as shown in **Figure 5a**. Steady state temperature maps for these are shown in **Figure 6**. **Figure 5a** is a low-resolution map (100 μm pixels) over most of the cross-sectional area while **Figure 5b** shows the map and line profiles at a much higher resolution (10 μm) in the region of the fiber.

4 DISCUSSION

Calibration of the AuNR temperature response for each material batch is crucial to the accuracy of the method because the reshaping dynamics are strongly affected by material composition. The dependence of the reshaping dynamics on temperature limits the time scale over which the technique is useful. In order to use the calibration as described, the sample must be exposed to a steady-state temperature profile for a long enough time that the nanorods can approach their asymptotic shapes. The specific time constants can vary greatly from one material to the next, and a good calibration of the expected temperature profile is important in order to obtain accurate temperature measurements.

The calculation of the AuNR aspect ratio from the spectra relies on two key assumptions. First, the rods must be small enough that their plasmon resonances are well described by a simple dipole approximation. Second, the host material must be transparent (negligible imaginary index of refraction) at scattered wavelengths. When both of those conditions are satisfied, the sensitivity of the calculation to the energy of the transverse mode resonance, which has a smaller absorbance, is the primary source of uncertainty in the temperature measurement. Nanorod loadings must be chosen such that the effective optical density of the AuNR peaks is sufficient to unambiguously determine the peak energies.

In comparing FLIR measurements to the spectrally derived temperatures, it is important to note some fundamental differences. First, because the epoxy is only semi-transparent at mid- and far-infrared wavelengths, the FLIR data represents only the temperatures at the surface which are visible to the camera. On the other hand, since the AuNR technique relies on visible spectrum optical

transmission, it samples the entire volume of the sample. Furthermore, the spatial resolution of the FLIR is limited by the focusing optics and the CCD array size. The resolution of the AuNR measurement is, in principle, limited only by the microspectrophotometer optics, since the image is obtained by raster scanning over the sample. Finally, the FLIR measurement is made during heating, while the AuNR measurement can be made at any time during or after heating.

The single fiber specimen shown in **Figure 4** is a surrogate model that is useful for studying the effects of fiber composition, coatings, interfaces, and resin chemistry on thermal transport in composites. In composites with higher volume fractions of carbon fibers the temperature measurement technique as described is more difficult, but still realizable. Consider, for example, a composite specimen with a few carbon fibers with variable spacing. If this material were subject to radiative heating from one side (eg, during laser machining), the resulting scattering, absorption, conduction, and re-radiation of energy would produce a complex temperature profile as illustrated in **Figure 5**. Measuring the temperature profile in such a sample would require a larger AuNR loading fraction because the cross-section slices would have to be thin in order to avoid perturbations in the light path from the many fibers in the field of view. Conversely, fiber orientation effects could be avoided altogether by measuring the scattering spectrum in reflectance mode or by using a near field scanning optical microscope (NSOM).

The temperature resolution of this new technique depends on the quality of the nanorods and the reproducibility of their reshaping behavior in the desired host matrix. The intrinsic heterogeneity[12]–[14] of commercially available AuNRs limits the precision of the plasmon peak determination and also gives rise to a spread in the temperature response for a given population of nanosensors. In our case, this results in a variance of $\sim 7^\circ\text{C}$ between the calculated temperature and the temperature measured by the FLIR or predicted by FEA. This limitation would be minimized by using high purity, uniform size distributions of nanorods. The accurate determination of the SPR energies is vital to the determination of the temperature. Even with monodisperse particles, the uncertainty associated with the measurement of the plasmon resonance energies will ultimately limit the precision of the temperature measurement.

Due to the Arrhenius-like shape evolution of AuNRs, the temperature resolution of this technique is also a function of the heating time and desired temperature range. AuNRs exposed to high temperatures at short times will change the same amount as those exposed to lower temperatures for longer times. For a certain desired temperature precision it will be necessary to heat the sample for a time that depends on the temperature being measured. Using the calibration data for AuNR-EPON we estimate that measuring a temperature T ($^\circ\text{C}$) with a temperature uncertainty of $\pm n^\circ\text{C}$ requires a heating time t (in seconds) according to $\text{Log}[t] \approx -.02T + (7 - n/5)$. Thus, for a temperature uncertainty of $\pm 5^\circ\text{C}$ the sample heating time should be at least a few minutes at 200°C . For the same uncertainty at 100°C , the time should be at least two and a half hours. Failure to heat for the required time results in systematic under estimation of the temperature by this method, especially at lower temperatures.

Even without precise temperature calibration, useful information about the polymer state can be obtained from these nanocomposites. Because the irreversible thermal reshaping of the AuNRs depends on both temperature and time of exposure, their absorption spectra can be correlated to a total degree of cure. Ehlert, et.al reported measuring the degree of cure of Cycom® 5320-1 for different thermal cycles by comparing the full-width at half maximum (FWHM) of the transverse plasmon resonance in embedded AuNRs[15]. Thus, the optically detected thermal transition of AuNRs provides a local record of at least one aspect of the material's thermal history.

5 CONCLUSION

We have shown that AuNRs may be used as embedded, nanoscale, highly sensitive, continuously varying, irreversible temperature sensors over the temperature range of $100\text{--}200^\circ\text{C}$. For steady state thermal profiles of sufficient duration this method enables the ex-situ determination of temperature with spatial resolution down to at least $10\ \mu\text{m}$. These temperatures agree well with surface temperature measured using a commercial infrared camera as well as with the predictions of FEM simulations. In principle, the ultimate spatial resolution is limited only by the density of nanorods, and the nature of the surface plasmon resonance probe. Thus, nanoscale resolution may be achieved with the

appropriate confocal or near-field approach. This technique complements other nanoscale thermographic methods by combining high spatial resolution, a wide range of continuous temperature response, and the ability to record maximum steady state temperature for ex-situ measurement. It is particularly well suited to the study of polymer nanocomposites where the AuNRs can be well dispersed in a transparent matrix and where the dynamics of the thermally induced shape change are slow. Thus, it provides an important tool for studies of micro- and nano-scale thermal transport in such materials.

Figure 1: Theoretical scattering spectra for nanorods of different aspect ratios alongside a schematic for the temperature sensing mechanism. In the upper left plot the dielectric constant is held fixed and the aspect ratio is varied. In the lower left plot the aspect ratio is fixed and the local dielectric constant is varied. The right schematic shows thermally reshaped nanorods with low aspect ratios (high temperatures) and high aspect ratios (low temperatures) in a radial thermal gradient.

Figure 2: Time evolution of aspect ratio in AuNR-EPON. (a) Example spectra for a calibration sample at 160°C at different times. The inset shows the evolution of the transverse (T) and longitudinal (L) plasmon peak resonances. (b) Aspect ratio as a function of time at 160°C showing the bi-exponential fit in red. The dashed blue curve is the (poor) single exponential fit. The inset shows similar curves for a variety of temperatures.

Figure 3: Temperature calibration $a_\infty(T)$. The relationship is approximately linear over the range of interest. Insets show sample data used to confirm the spectroscopic determination of the nanorod aspect ratios by TEM and SAXS.

Figure 4: Temperature maps for a rectangular specimen heated at one end and cooled at the other (and subject to natural convection in the room). (a) Image obtained by a commercial FLIR camera. (b) Image obtained through the AuNR spectral analysis. (c) Comparison of the average temperature profile along the length of the sample as measured by the two methods.

Figure 5: Single fiber dog-bone used to produce and measure a complex thermal profile. (a) AuNR-EPON with a single fiber running down the length highlighted in blue. The two cross-section locations are marked A and B respectively. (b) FLIR image of the sample during heating. (c) FEM model of the steady state sample temperature.

Figure 6: Temperature maps for cross-sections of the single fiber dog-bone specimen. (a) Optical micrograph showing color change in the region of the fiber. (b) Spectrally calculated temperature map for cross-section A at $100 \mu\text{m}$ resolution. (c) Measured (points) and calculated (dashed lines) radial temperature profiles near the fiber. The insets show the temperature maps near the fibers at $10 \mu\text{m}$ resolution.

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